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Scientific Publications in the Top 10% by Citations in Italian Regions

Increased by an average of 5.03% between 2018 and 2023

The European Innovation Scoreboard calculates the number of scientific publications in the top 10% by citations in Italian regions. The variable is defined as the number of scientific publications in the top 10% most cited worldwide (Scopus). This indicator measures the efficiency of the research system, as highly cited publications are assumed to be of superior quality. There may be a bias towards small or English-speaking countries given the coverage of Scopus publication data. The data refer to the 20 Italian regions between 2018 and 2023.

Scientific Publications in the Top 10% by Citations in Italian Regions in 2023. The analysis of data on the top 10% most cited scientific publications in Italian regions in 2023 offers an interesting perspective on the research landscape in the country, highlighting some surprising results that challenge traditional expectations. Calabria ranks first with an index of 153.4724, followed by Abruzzo and Campania, showing a strong presence of high-impact research in regions often considered peripheral in the context of Italian scientific research. This might reflect specific excellence in certain fields or the ability of these regions to produce scientific work that resonates internationally. On the other hand, regions traditionally associated with intense research and development activity, such as Emilia Romagna, Lombardy, and Veneto, are lower in the ranking, suggesting that despite the high overall volume of publications, a smaller proportion of their work falls into the top 10% most cited. This does not necessarily indicate lower research quality but might reflect a broader distribution of areas of interest or a different approach to dissemination and international collaboration. Friuli Venezia Giulia, despite its solid research ecosystem highlighted by other indicators, surprisingly ranks last in this specific metric, suggesting a possible focus on niche research areas or a need to strengthen the visibility and impact strategies of its publications.

Scientific Publications in the Top 10% by Citations in Italian Regions between 2018 and 2023. The analysis of the absolute and percentage change in the top 10% most cited scientific publications in Italian regions between 2018 and 2023 offers a dynamic view of the evolution of the impact of scientific research at the regional level. Some clear trends emerge from these data, showing both significant progress and challenges. Basilicata shows a remarkable increase, both in absolute terms (+25.77) and percentage (+30.97%), highlighting an impressive growth in the impact of its scientific research. This suggests a significant improvement in the quality and/or international relevance of publications originating from this region. Marche and Molise also record significant increases, with

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percentage changes of 37.27% and 21.45% respectively, indicating notable advancements in the production of high-impact research. Conversely, Trentino Alto Adige and Valle d'Aosta show the highest negative percentage changes, -12.62% and -37.00% respectively, signaling a reduction in the impact of their scientific publications. This could reflect various factors, including changes in research priorities, international collaboration, or funding policies. The situation in Campania is surprising, showing a slight decrease in both absolute (-0.30) and percentage (-0.22%) terms, suggesting substantial stability in its research impact despite fluctuations at national and global levels in the scientific field. Friuli Venezia Giulia and Lombardy, regions traditionally strong in research, both show declines, with percentage changes of -3.24% and -4.63% respectively.

Italian Macro-Regions. The analysis of the trend of the top 10% most cited scientific publications in Italian macro-regions from 2018 to 2023 reveals interesting regional dynamics in the production of high-impact research. The South shows a notable upward trajectory, starting with an index of 108.1969325 in 2018 and steadily growing to 124.17695 in 2023. This substantial increase reflects significant growth in the visibility and impact of research produced in the southern regions, suggesting an improvement in research quality or a greater ability to engage in internationally relevant scientific contexts. The Center starts with an index slightly lower than the South in 2018 but also shows a steady increase over the years, reaching an index of 121.64705 in 2023. This growth, despite a slight fluctuation in 2021, indicates a strengthening of high-level scientific production in the central regions of Italy, consolidating their position in the landscape of national and international excellence research. The North, starting from a position of strength in 2018 with an index of 120.0390788, presents a more fluctuating trend. After a significant decline until 2020, with the lowest index of 98.02367, it rises in the following two years, stabilizing at 109.5044613 in 2023. This path might reflect a series of challenges in maintaining constant research impact in the context of a competitive and rapidly evolving environment, but also the resilience and recovery capacity of the research infrastructures in the North. These data highlight not only the importance of quality research and its international recognition but also how regional dynamics influence scientific production in Italy. While the South and the Center show a positive and consistent trend, the North, despite an initial leadership, faces challenges in maintaining a consistently high footprint in the context of the most cited publications.

North-South Divide. Data on the top 10% most cited scientific publications between 2018 and 2023 in Italian macro-regions indicate an interesting trend concerning the North-South divide. Initially, the North showed a higher index, suggesting a greater incidence of high-impact publications compared to the Center and the South. However, over the years, a reversal of this trend is observed, with the South and the Center not only closing the gap but surpassing the North by 2023. This evolution suggests that while there was an initial gap in terms of highly cited scientific publications, with the North having an advantage over the South, this gap has significantly narrowed over time. By 2023, the South records the highest growth index, surpassing both the Center and the North. This change might reflect various factors, including targeted research investments, improvements in higher education quality, and increased international collaboration in the southern regions. Additionally, the fluctuation observed in the North, with a marked decrease followed by a recovery and finally stabilization, might indicate that northern regions have faced specific challenges temporarily affecting their high-impact scientific production. It might also suggest increasing competitiveness in the national research landscape, with the Center and the South intensifying their efforts to produce internationally recognized quality research. In conclusion, while a North-South divide in terms of highly cited scientific publications initially existed, recent trends indicate a reversal of this dynamic, with the South showing remarkable growth, positioning itself as the leader in 2023.

Economic Policies to Increase Scientific Publications in the Top 10% Internationally. To elevate the international profile of Italian scientific research and increase the presence of Italian publications in the top 10% most cited, it is necessary to adopt a set of targeted economic policies and support strategies. This implies a significant increase in direct research funding, prioritizing projects demonstrating potential for international and multidisciplinary collaboration. Supporting the development of advanced research infrastructures capable of supporting cutting-edge scientific activities also becomes essential. A crucial component of these policies must be investing in the training and attraction of talent, both national and international, through competitive scholarships and attractive academic career opportunities. Similarly, incentivizing collaborations between universities and industry through tax incentives can stimulate innovation and technology transfer. Promoting the international mobility of researchers contributes to expanding collaboration networks and knowledge sharing, key factors for high-impact publications. Moreover, it is fundamental to establish a merit-based evaluation system for allocating research funds, thus rewarding excellence and scientific productivity. Finally, supporting scientific dissemination helps raise public awareness of the importance of research and its social and economic impact.

Conclusions. The value of scientific publications in the top 10% in Italian regions increased by an average of 5.03% between 2018 and 2023. In 2023, Calabria was the leading region for publications in the top 10% by citations, with a value of 153.47, followed by Abruzzo with 136.83, and Campania with a value of 136.62 units. Looking at the Italian macro-regions, we can note a growth of +14.77% in the South and +16.59% in Central Italy between 2018 and 2023. However, in Northern Italy, the value of publications in the top 10% by citation value decreased by 8.78% between 2018 and 2023. Additionally, the dominant macro-region in 2023 is Southern Italy, with a value of 124.17%, followed by Central Italy, and Northern Italy in third place. This unusual scenario highlights the ability of the Southern research system to be competitive internationally.

Declarations

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Appendix

